

Response letter to the reviewers of “Performing live time-traversal queries on RDF datasets” (SWJ)

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We want to thank the responsible editor and the reviewers for their time and care in preparing their reviews of our initial version of the paper, available at <https://www.semantic-web-journal.net/content/performing-live-time-traversal-queries-rdf-datasets>. We appreciate their thoughtful criticisms and helpful comments. In particular, we believe that the inclusion of rigorous definitions and the extension of the benchmarking procedure definitely strengthens the paper. If a response to a reviewer’s comment is missing, it is because that response has already been given to another reviewer’s similar comment. Please, find our replies as follows.

1 Reviewer #1

The related work is comprehensive and pertinent. That said, the paper has disregarded a few citations, in particular those related to SPARQL extensions for time-travel queries.

We were aware of SPARQL extensions to query time-aware RDF datasets. However, we did not consider them relevant to our work, which aims instead to use standard SPARQL. Nonetheless, your remark made us discuss the appropriateness of citing these works to highlight this feature of time-agnostic-library. Therefore, we mentioned τ -SPARQL [9], T-SPARQL [4], AnQL [11], SPARQLTL [3], and $SPARQL^T$ [10] in Section 2.2 “Querying dynamic linked data”.

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I think the non-reliance on syntactic extensions for SPARQL is one of the strengths of the paper. However, I think the current version lacks a formalization of the semantics of the different query types. This is important since this work also provides a concrete implementation for those queries. I would encourage the authors to formalize the notions of time-aware dataset and time-travel query, and define rigorously what we expect as result when we run each query type.

We added the time-aware dataset definition and formalized all the retrieval functionalities, particularly regarding the expected results.

It seems as the used benchmark is part of the paper's contribution. If so, it should be more comprehensive: two SPARQL queries are simply not enough. While they cover the two general cases – known/unknown subjects –, there are still some factors that can be varied in order to provide a more comprehensive evaluation: the predicates occurring the queries, the dynamicity of the chosen subject, the form of the triple patterns, etc. If more SPARQL queries are included, the paper should also provide a more detailed description of them (number of triple patterns, shape, type of predicates, etc).

Are queries executed multiple times and their times averaged? (the standard deviation should be provided). What about reordering the execution of the queries (in this case, alternating between queries 1 and 2) to challenge the Blazegraph cache?

To answer this justified objection, we have enriched the query variety. The query with a known subject now occurs on 20 randomly selected entities among those relevant to this query, namely bibliographic entities with citations. Such entities have a variable number of provenance snapshots, ranging from a minimum of 2 to a maximum of 35. They have 20 snapshots on average; the median is 20, and the standard deviation is 8. Each query is executed ten times for each query type and each entity. Therefore, they are run 200 times for each query on known subjects and ten times on unknown subjects.

Regarding statistics, in the first version of the article, we had reported the minimum and the range instead of the mean and the standard deviation, as suggested by the documentation of Python's *timeit* module: "It's tempting to calculate mean and standard deviation from the result vector and report these. However, this is not very useful. In a typical case, the lowest value gives a lower bound for how fast your machine can run the given code snippet; higher values in the result vector are typically not caused by variability in Python's speed, but by other processes interfering with your timing accuracy. So the `min()` of the result is probably the only number you should be interested in. After that, you should look at the entire vector and apply common sense rather than statistics."

However, the average becomes significant in the new context because each query is executed on 20 different entities and not on the same entity, making

it interesting to see the average runtime in a scenario where queries involve different numbers of snapshots. Therefore, we have indicated the mean and standard deviation for each query.

On the other hand, using two query shapes, one for joined and one for isolated triple patterns, was a deliberate choice. Using the same queries across different configurations makes the results comparable, allowing us to highlight the strengths and limitations of the proposed methodology. For example, if the query with unknown subjects on all versions differed from the query on all deltas, it would be impossible to verify that the latter is faster than the former because it does not require materialising entities. In addition, the current benchmark system aims to be as comprehensive as possible by considering seven variables: the triplestore, the retrieval functionality, the entity, the text index, the cache, the overhead and the query runtime on the current snapshot. Adding additional query shapes to the variables while keeping the results comparable would make the benchmarks practically unfeasible.

As you mentioned, Blazegraph and other triplestores cache query results making the subsequent execution nearly instant. To solve this problem at its root, we killed each triplestore and relaunched it before each query since this cache is volatile and released when the database is closed.

Without a reference, the numbers in table 5 are completely uninformative. Perhaps a baseline for comparison could be the query runtime on the latest snapshot/change. This could provide a hint of the overhead induced by time-traversal, including a per-snapshot/per-update overhead, that is, the result of dividing the total runtime by the number of revisions/updates involved in the query execution

We liked the idea of using the baseline you suggested. Upon further analysis, we realized that this baseline differs depending on the query type.

Regarding the queries on versions, we used precisely the measures you mentioned, i.e., the query runtime on the latest version and the per-snapshot overhead. The number of snapshots involved was calculated differently depending on the query type. Regarding version materialization, the number of snapshots is equal to the number of snapshots of that entity. Conversely, for materializations of particular versions, the number of snapshots equals the number of snapshots between the present and the version to be materialized. The same holds for cross-version and single-version queries: the snapshots' number is equal to the sum of all present and past entities' snapshots involved in the query or just the ones included between the present and the desired period.

The perspective is reversed for delta queries. For those, the baseline is provided by a query on the deltas of the entities currently in the dataset. Therefore, the overhead is given by the total number of entities involved in the query, particularly those no longer present in the dataset that needs to be identified algorithmically.

The paper should show that the overall approach (data model + proposed strategy) is viable for SW practitioners, and that brings

something new w.r.t. the state of the art. I therefore believe that a broader comparison with existing solutions is mandatory. This could include either an evaluation of the approach using another graph store, e.g., Virtuoso, Fuseki, (I understand it may be tricky since not all solutions have sophisticated text search functionalities, an alternative could be QLever <https://github.com/ad-freiburg/qllever>) or a comparison with OSTRICH (limited to the queries when this is possible). This would certainly change the content of the discussion section.

We significantly enriched the evaluation procedure to address this comment. Now, benchmarks are performed on Blazegraph, GraphDB Free Edition, Apache Jena Fuseki, and OpenLink Virtuoso. Each of these triplestores offers full-text search functionality, and we extended time-agnostic-library to support all of them. Also, benchmarks show the differences between using the textual index or not for each of these triplestores.

We did not use QLever in the comparison because it does not support updates via SPARQL and is not relevant to our software which aims to support real-time operations. Similarly, a comparison with OSTRICH would have been unfair since OSTRICH requires pre-indexing all data before it can be used.

2 Reviewer #2

My primary concern with this work is with the discussion around the query approaches. Each query approach is currently explained in the text and with a flow chart. Nevertheless, there seem to be many details missing in order to precisely understand how each algorithm works. I think explaining the algorithms together with detailed pseudocode might help solve this problem. This could also form the basis for a proof of correctness, which also appears to be missing at the moment.

For example, it is unclear how the delta materialization algorithm works. The authors say that “no operations are needed” for this due to the way the data is stored. But it is unclear then what needs to happen exactly for the results to be formed. For instance, I would expect some kind of merge operation to occur when a resource has multiple snapshots/update queries.

We believe this lack of clarity stemmed from the absence of strict definitions for each query type. We have added such definitions and specified that delta materialization concerns the delta of two consecutive versions, then no merges are needed.

Pseudocode and flowchart are two methods of representing an algorithm. While pseudocode uses a fictitious high-level programming language, the flowchart uses drawings. We believe that the flowchart allows readers to understand the workings of the various algorithms more intuitively.

The storage approach is missing details around the way SPARQL update queries are stored. Based on the examples, it seems like only INSERT DATA and DELETE DATA queries are allowed, and update queries with a WHERE clause are not. Furthermore, it seems like certain operations depend on string matching of URLs, which requires no prefixes to be used within queries. It is also unclear if blank nodes are allowed. It seems crucial for these kinds of details around the storage approach to be formalized.

You are right, clarifying these details is crucial. Therefore, we have specified that “SPARQL update queries representing deltas must contain only absolute URIs, literals, and blank nodes, while prefixes and variables are not permitted”. Since variables are not permitted, neither are WHERE clauses.

It is unclear why the authors did not include a comparison of their approach with other RDF archiving systems, and made use of existing RDF archiving benchmarks such as BEAR.

We designed a custom benchmark and did not use BEAR because BEAR does not allow experimenting with our methodology’s three most relevant aspects: the possibility of performing time-traversal queries via SPARQL live. In fact, it does not support cross-version (or time-traversal) and cross-delta queries, does not use SPARQL but AnQL, and does not consider the cost of indexing the data before launching the query for those systems that do not operate in real-time.

In section 2.3, the authors talk about the retrieval functionality categorization from Fernández, Polleres and Umbrich. More recent RDF archiving papers make use of the more low-level “foundational query atoms”, which are considered more fundamental for covering all retrieval demands. The usage of this other terminology is probably the cause of a mistake in table 5 (which may fit better in the related work section) regarding the available functionality in other systems. For instance, the OSTRICH system supports all retrieval functionality (but not live indeed).

We were aware of the “query atoms” classification (C1), but we preferred to use the one on “retrieval needs” (C2) because it is more comprehensive, as it adds the query to reconstruct a full version of an entity, an entire delta, and the query on multiples/all deltas. These queries can also be obtained through query atoms by composition. For example, the cross-delta structured query in C2 can be obtained by first accomplishing a change-materialisation to get all the versions where a query returns different results and then a delta materialisation on all the versions thus obtained. Regardless, we preferred to be explicit and concise by adopting C2.

We do not think the two classifications are in opposition, but they have different goals. C1 focuses on atomic elements, while C2 on the actual objectives

of an application to query a time-aware dataset, and we prefer the latter point of view. We clarified the reason for this choice in the article at the beginning of section 2.2.

At any rate, thank you for the clarification regarding OSTRICH, we corrected the information in the comparison table, which is now in the related works section.

The paper mentions in several places that it does not require pre-indexing, such as on page 30: “Therefore, to date, as far as we know, time-agnostic library is the only software to support all retrieval functionalities without requiring pre-indexing processes.” As far as I understand, the time-agnostic library in fact *does* require pre-indexing of the latest version, which is stored in a triple store (e.g. Blazegraph), which does make use of indexes. Furthermore, the requirement to attach SPARQL update queries on entities, and the usage of the Blazegraph text index also forms an indexing process. Therefore, it seems imprecise to consider this work as not requiring pre-indexing.

It is true; the definition of “live” that we adopted in the first version of our article was ambiguous and left room for this misunderstanding. By “live”, we do not mean that no indexes are used but that such indexes do not affect the real-time operation of the software. In other words, “live” means that it is possible to update the data and make time-agnostic queries on it without stopping the service and re-index all the data, as x-RDF-3X, v-RDFCSA, RDF-TX, OSTRICH, and Dydra do. Therefore, we have more explicitly defined “live” in the new version of the article.

Are there any measurements of how large the cache can become?

As we specified in the new version of the paper, at the end of all benchmarks, the cache contained 45 dataset versions in which 10,291 entities were reconstructed, totalling 691,799 quadruples. The weight varies depending on the triplestore and is 209.7 MB for Blazegraph, 128.3 MB for GraphDB, 405.8 MB for Fuseki, and 82,1 MB for Virtuoso.

It would be nice if the time-agnostic-browser would run on a web server, so that readers can use it without having to setup the system locally.

We removed the time-agnostic browser from the discussion for several reasons: first, because of maximum word count issues. Second, the time-agnostic browser served only a demo function but had no real utility and was not worth running on a live server. In addition, we are working on a curation interface for metadata that integrates the time-agnostic library for change-tracking and provenance management, so we postponed the interface discussion to future articles.

The proposed approach seems be related to TailR and Quit store, so it would be good to include them in related work.

We extended the comparison to include TailR [6] and Quit Store [1].

Does this approach support the full SPARQL 1.1 syntax? E.g., the authors talk about handling triple patterns, but not property paths, so it is unclear whether or not these are supported as well.

The time-agnostic library currently allows only inverse property paths to be used. We specified that in the article and said we intend to support the other property paths in the future.

3 Reviewer #3

I think that the Introduction is not very convincing. Limitations of state of the art are quickly/poorly described, to the detriment of a long description of OCDM (that could be described more precisely later).

We shortened the description of OCDM, adding some details on why the pre-processing required by other systems is unsuitable for handling datasets that receive many updates in real time. For example: “Ostrich requires 22 hours to ingest revision 9 of Dbpedia”.

Another limitation of the state we emphasized is that many systems adopt a data model not compliant with RDF to express metadata (e.g., Wikidata, x-RDF-3X, Dydra) or impose a custom database (e.g., Quit Store, OSTRICH) or a specific triplestore (e.g., R&WBase and R43ples).

I’m quite surprised to not see some examples of different types of time-traversal queries as described in [2] (just to explain the context) ie [2] is cited, but I had to read [2] again to really understand this paper.

We added an example for each query type.

The Semantic Web Journal published [7], but this publication is not cited (I’m not an author of this paper).

Thank you for the recommendation. In the new paper version, we mentioned that article, which allowed us to elaborate further or correct the comparison in Table 1, which was already described in [7].

Table 1 is interesting, but how is the “scalable column” decided? I don’t see why RDF* is not scalable. Can you give evidence that RDF* does not scale? Also concerning the standard, I agree that RDF* is currently not a standard, but there is a W3C working group, with a first draft published and quite solid implementations available. Is it possible to represent the OCDM model in RDF* ??

In [8], approaches that cause triple bloat are defined as “not scalable”. The same article considers RDF* as not scalable without explaining why. After a more in-depth analysis, we consider RDF* as a scalable solution, disagreeing with [8]. At any rate, for the sake of synthesis, we removed the whole comparison between annotation syntaxes, including the scalability analysis, and described only the most relevant approaches. For a more in-depth discussion and comparison, we referred to [8]. In addition, we have clarified the existence of the W3C working group to expand RDF 1.1 and SPARQL 1.1 with the semantics of RDF*.

Regarding a way to represent the OCDM model in RDF*, OCDM and RDF* represent provenance with different granularities. While the OCDM attaches provenance to entities, RDF* attaches provenance to triples. Therefore, the two models are not perfectly interchangeable. In particular, the property `oco:hasUpdateQuery` does not make sense in RDF* because the information about the validity or invalidity of a triple is already expressed for every single triple. On the other hand, it is possible to represent in RDF* all the provenance-related properties provided by the OCDM., as shown in 1.

```
@base <https://github.com/opencitations/time-agnostic-library/>.
@prefix dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>.
@prefix prov: <http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#>.

# RDF*

<<<br/86766> dcterms:title
"Open access and online publishing: a new frontier in nursing?">>
  prov:hadPrimarySource <https://api.crossref.org>.

# OCDM

<br/86766> dcterms:title
"Open access and online publishing: a new frontier in nursing?".

<br/86766/prov/se/1>
  prov:hadPrimarySource <https://api.crossref.org>;
  prov:specializationOf <br/86766>.
```

Listing 1: An example conversion from RDF* to the OCDM using the Turtle* serialization

As it is written, at the end of the related works, we don’t really know what is the scientific problem to solve. A strong restructuring of the paper is needed to leave the related with a crystal clear problem to solve.

We restructured the entire paper by posing the scientific problem highlighted

by related work as a common thread. This problem is that, to the best of our knowledge, many methodologies for performing live time agnostic queries require pre-processing the data. Conversely, software to query on the fly is not generic, either because it does not comply with RDF and SPARQL or requires custom or specific databases to operate.

In addition, we significantly synthesized the related works section to make it more straightforward.

The model is not easy to understand. Many drawings are provided, but finally, the reader has to read listing 1 to see really where the first “hasUpdateQuery” is located. So examples are quite difficult to follow. For example, it requires time to understand the sel/se2 contains the history of the entity. (I think there is a Typo P10 line 38 “10.1111/j.1365 2648.2012.06023.x” instead of “10.1111/j.1365 2648.2012.06023.x”).

Thank you for the feedback. We have better emphasized the first `hasUpdateQuery` by reversing the order of the snapshots in Listing 1 — i.e., by placing the most recent snapshot at the top — and by adding red borders around the `INSERT DATA` and `DELETE DATA` clauses so that the crucial part of the listing stands out. In addition, we added the update query to the Graffoo diagram in Figure 2.

Also, we corrected the typo: the trailing dot was missing in the first DOI.

Section 3.1 presents how it is possible to materialise Version and Delta from the OCDM model. I’m not a big fan of flow charts to describe how to do things. It lacks definitions, it lacks precision, and at the end it is nearly impossible to estimate complexities of operations. For these operations, is the proposal better than competitors (PromptDiff, SemVersion, R&WBase) at the algorithmical level?

Section 3.2 makes the lack of definition/algo more problematic. What is precisely an isolated triple pattern? What is an explicit solvable variable? As definitions are not present, it takes a lot of time (reading and re-reading) to really understand how the approach works. The same remark with flow charts also applies here.

I understood that the main issue with this approach is to materialise only the required entities at the right point in time during query evaluation. Of course the approach works well, if there is a root entity to start from. If not, the number of entities to materialise can be in the worst case the whole dataset. Such complexities are important to understand the limitation of the approach and, as it is not present, it is a serious drawback for the paper.

Again, on the algorithmic part, how can this approach be compared with v-RDFCSA in terms of complexities ?? It seems to me that the proposed approach can be catastrophic if non-selective queries.

An analysis of the complexity of the algorithms would be compelling but deserve a whole article dedicated to it. Indeed, none of the articles mentioned in the related works has done this kind of analysis, making the comparison you suggested impossible. Moreover, the source code of several of the software mentioned is not available as open source, i.e., SemVersion, PromptDiff, RB-DMS, Dydra, RDF-TX, and v-RDFCSA. Even if one wanted to, it would not be possible to calculate the complexity of their algorithms a posteriori.

On the other hand, we agree on the importance of strictly defining all query types and critical concepts, such as the isolated triple pattern you mentioned, and we have added these definitions. “Explicit solvable variables” was, indeed, a passage in the flowchart elliptical and ambiguous. We made it more transparent and explicit by separating it into several passages, i.e., “For each relevant time, for each triple, does it have only one variable?” \rightarrow “Yes” \rightarrow “Explicit that variable at that time”. In other words, “Explicit solvable variables” meant “Solve those variables that can be solved, as they were present in triple patterns within the input SPARQL query that contained only that variable”.

Regarding v-RDFCSA, as we said, the code of v-RDFCSA is unavailable, and the article does not provide a complexity analysis. Furthermore, v-RDFCSA does not support cross-version and cross-delta queries but only single-version, version-materialization, and delta-materialization on single triple patterns. Its main goal is to reduce storage space at the cost of preventing real-time updates. For all these reasons, we believe that a comparison between time-agnostic-library and v-RDFCSA would be of little significance.

Section 4 describes the implementation. It looks like a user manual and is quite boring to read. We understand that the cache is important for the library, but it lacks, at least, a simple formalisation to understand how the cache works.

Section 4 about the implementation and use of the library was removed entirely and published on Zenodo, together with the cache system description [5]. It now serves the purpose of thorough documentation and is cited at the end of Section 3 Methodology.

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